

The National Composite Index for Family Planning (NCIFP): results and methodological issues
Extended Data

Extended Data Table 1. The 35 Questionnaire Items, by Dimension

Dimension	Question	Yes/No	1 to 10
Strategy	Does the National Family Planning Action plan include defined objectives over a 5-to 10-year period, including quantitative targets?	X	new
	Does the National Family Planning Action plan include objectives to reach the poorest and most vulnerable groups with quality FP information and services?	X	new
	Does the National Family Planning Action plan include projection of the resources (material, human and financial) required to implement the strategy, as well as sets forth a plan to secure the resources?	X	new
	Does the National Family Planning Action plan include a mechanism and funding to support meaningful participation of diverse stakeholders?	X	new
	High level of seniority of the director of the national family planning program and whether director reports to a high level of government.		X
	Extent to which import laws and legal regulations facilitate the importation of contraceptive supplies or extent to which contraceptives are manufactured locally.		X
	Data	Does the government collect data to monitor special sub-groups?*	X
Does the government collect data from the private sector on commodities?		X	new
Is there a system of quality control for service statistics?		X	new
Are data used to ensure that the poorest and most vulnerable women and girls have access to quality FP services?		X	new
Extent to which systems for client recordkeeping, clinic reporting and feedback of results are adequate.			X
Extent to which program statistics, national surveys, and small studies are used by specialized staff to report on program operations and measure progress.			X
Extent to which program managers use research and evaluation findings to improve the program in ways suggested by findings.			X
	Are FP SOP in line with WHO and used for determining areas of need for quality improvement?	X	new
	Are there guidelines on task sharing of family planning services?	X	new

Quality	Are indicators for quality of care collected and used for public sector family planning services?	X	new
	Are indicators for quality of care collected and used for private sector family planning services?	X	new
	Are there structures in place to address quality, including participatory monitoring or community/facility quality improvement activities?	X	new
	Does government collect information related to informed choice and provider bias?	X	new
	Extent to which training programs, for each category of staff in the family planning program, are adequate to provide personnel with information and skills necessary to carry out their jobs effectively.		X
	Extent to which the logistics and transport systems are sufficient to keep stocks of contraceptive supplies and related equipment available at all service points, at all times and at all levels (central, provincial, local).		X
	Extent to which the system of supervision at all levels is adequate (regular monitoring visits with corrective or supportive action).		X
	Extent to which clients adopting sterilization are routinely informed that it is permanent?		X
	Extent to which the entire population has ready and easy access to IUD removal.		X
	Extent to which the entire population has ready and easy access to implant removal.		X
Equity	Are there policies in place to prevent discrimination towards each of special sub-groups?*	X	new
	To what extent do service providers discriminate against special sub-groups?*		X
	Extent to which areas of country not easily serviced by clinics or other service points are covered by CBD programs for distribution of contraceptives (especially rural areas).		X
	Extent to which the entire population has ready access to LAPMs.**		X
	Extent to which the entire population has ready access to STMs.**		X
Accountability	Are there mechanisms in place at the national, subnational, and facility level to monitor whether or not access to voluntary, non-discriminatory FP information and services is being achieved?	X	new
	Does the government have mechanisms in place for reporting instances of denial of services on non-medical grounds (age, marital status, ability to pay), or coercion	X	new

	(including inappropriate use of incentives to clients or providers)?		
	Are violations reviewed on a regular basis?	X	new
	Are there mechanisms in place at the facility level to solicit and use feedback from clients?	X	new
	Is there a system in place that encourages dialogue and communication between users and service providers/health officials about service availability, accessibility, acceptability, and quality?	X	new
<p>* Indicates composite score, based on separate ratings for each special subgroup: Youth, Unmarried Women, Wealth Status, Post-Abortion Clients, and HIV Status. **LAPMs include Female Sterilization, Male Sterilization, IUDs, Implants; STMs include Condoms, Pills, and Injectables</p>			

Extended Data Table 2. Distribution of Women of Reproductive Age within and between Regions

ASIA WRA = 549,862,000 (57% of total)	LAC WRA = 76,659,000 (8% of total)	MENA WRA = 46,676,000 (5% of total)	SSAF-A WRA = 144,544,000 (15% of total)	SSAF-F WRA = 68,343,000 (7% of total)	EECA WRA = 70,920,000 (7% of total)
Countries within each region (% of regional WRA)					
Afghanistan (1.5%)	Bolivia (3.7%)	Egypt (49.0%)	Cameroon (4.2%)	Burkina Faso (6.5%)	Armenia (1.1%)
Bangladesh (8.1%)	Colombia (17.3%)	Iraq (19.1%)	Eritrea (0.6%)	Burundi (3.7%)	Georgia (1.3%)
Bhutan (0.0%)	Dom. Rep. (3.6%)	Jordan (5.2%)	Eswatini (0.2%)	CAR (1.6%)	Kazakhstan (6.4%)
Cambodia (0.8%)	El Salvador (2.4%)	Morocco (19.0%)	Ethiopia (18.2%)	Chad (4.9%)	Kyrgyz Rep. (2.2%)
India (62.8%)	Guatemala (5.9%)	Palestine (2.4%)	Gambia (0.4%)	Congo (1.8%)	Moldova (1.5%)
Lao PDR (0.3%)	Haiti (3.8%)		Ghana (5.1%)	Cote d'Ivoire (8.6%)	Romania (6.4%)
Malaysia (1.5%)	Honduras (3.3%)		Kenya (9.1%)	DR Congo (26.4%)	Russia (48.6%)
Mongolia (0.2%)	Jamaica (1.0%)		Lesotho (0.4%)	Guinea (4.3%)	Tajikistan (3.2%)
Myanmar (2.7%)	Mexico (44.4%)		Liberia (0.8%)	Guinea-Bissau (0.7%)	Turkmenistan (2.2%)
Nepal (1.5%)	Nicaragua (2.3%)		Malawi (3.0%)	Madagascar (9.2%)	Ukraine (14.9%)
Pakistan (9.5%)	Panama (1.4%)		Namibia (0.4%)	Mali (6.0%)	Uzbekistan (12.3%)
PNG (0.4%)	Peru (10.9%)		Nigeria (30.8%)	Mauritania (1.5%)	
Philippines (5.0%)			Rwanda (2.1%)	Mozambique (10.0%)	
Sri Lanka (1.0%)			Sierra Leone (1.3%)	Niger (6.6%)	
Solomon Isl. (0.0%)			Somalia (2.3%)	Sao Tome & Prin. (0.1%)	
Timor-Leste (0.1%)			South Sudan (5.3%)	Senegal (5.5%)	
Viet Nam (4.6%)			Tanzania (9.0%)	Togo (2.7%)	
			Uganda (6.8%)		
			Zambia (2.8%)		
			Zimbabwe (2.6%)		

Extended Data Table 3. Items with the Lowest and Highest Response Rates

Items with the lowest response rates				
Question type	Dimension	Question	Mean Response Rate	% Non-responses occurring after “No” on the Yes/No item
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Account.	Are violations reviewed on a regular basis?	63.6%	62.0%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Account.	Does the government have mechanisms in place for reporting instances of denial of services on non-medical grounds or coercion?	68.6%	67.6%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Quality	Does government collect information related to informed choice and provider bias?	69.7%	67.3%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Quality	Are indicators for quality of care collected and used for private sector family planning services?	73.2%	68.2%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Account.	Are there mechanisms in place at the facility level to solicit and use feedback from clients?	81.1%	71.4%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Data	Does the government collect data to monitor special subgroups?	81.6%	69.3%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Data	Does the government collect data from the private sector on commodities?	81.9%	72.0%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Account.	Are there mechanisms in place at the national, sub-national, and facility level to monitor whether or not access to voluntary, non-discriminatory FP information and services is being achieved?	82.2%	66.0%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Equity	Are there policies in place to prevent discrimination towards special subgroups?	82.5%	57.7%
1-10 scale following Yes/No	Quality	Are there guidelines on task sharing of family planning services?	82.7%	42.0%

Items with the highest response rates

Question type	Dimension	Question	Mean Response Rate
Standalone 1-10 scale	Equity	Extent to which entire population has ready and easy access to STMs	97.8%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Quality	Extent to which training programs, for each category of staff in the family planning program, are adequate to provide personnel with information and skills necessary to carry out their jobs effectively	97.2%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Quality	Extent to which the system of supervision at all levels is adequate (regular monitoring visits with corrective or supportive action)	96.9%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Data	Extent to which program statistics, national surveys, and small studies are used by specialized staff to report on program operations and measure progress	96.9%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Data	Extent to which systems for client recordkeeping, clinic reporting, and feedback of results are adequate	96.7%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Quality	Extent to which the logistics and transport systems are sufficient to keep stocks of contraceptive supplies and related equipment available at all service points, at all times and at all levels (central, provincial, local)	96.7%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Quality	Extent to which the entire population has ready and easy access to IUD removal	96.7%
Yes/No	Data	Are data used to ensure that the poorest and most vulnerable women and girls have access to quality FP services?	96.3%
Standalone 1-10 Scale	Data	Extent to which program managers use research and evaluation findings to improve the program in ways suggested by findings	96.1%
Standalone 1-10 scale	Equity	Extent to which entire population has ready and easy access to LAPMs	95.9%

Extended Data Table 4. Countries with the Highest and Lowest Response Rates.

Countries with the highest response rates

Region	Country	Mean Response Rate
ASIA	Solomon Islands	99.9
EECA	Turkmenistan	99.8
EECA	Armenia	99.6
ASIA	Viet Nam	99.4
SSA-F	Chad	98.8
EECA	Uzbekistan	98.5
LAC	Bolivia	98.3
SSAF-F	DR Congo	98.0
EECA	Tajikistan	97.8
LAC	Guatemala	96.9

Countries with the lowest response rates

Region	Country	Mean Response Rate
EECA	Romania	69.1
ASIA	Malaysia	73.5
SSAF-F	Cote d'Ivoire	73.8
EECA	Russia	74.4
EECA	Moldova	75.3
LAC	Jamaica	76.5
MENA	Iraq	76.9
MENA	Palestine	78.5
MENA	Morocco	80.7
SSAF-F	Central African Republic	81.3